

New data on the Lepidoptera of Azerbaijan (Southern Transcaucasia). Superfamily Pyraloidea Latreille, 1809

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Abstract

We present the faunal list of Pyraloidea (Lepidoptera) of Azerbaijan, including 222 species of 114 genera, belonging to two families. Forty eight species of Pyraloidea Moths are reported for Azerbaijan for the first time.

Keywords

Biodiversity, Caucasus, species richness, fauna, Pyralidae, Crambidae

Introduction

The Caucasus Ecoregion (including the Russian Caucasus, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, northeastern Turkey and northwestern Iran) is included in the list of “biodiversity hotspots” (Myers 1988; Myers et al. 2000). The Lepidoptera of this richest region are studied very unevenly. Traditionally, the most detailed summaries are on Papilionoidea (Ilyina and Morgun 2010, 2011; Tshikolovets and Nekrutenko 2012). Relatively complete information is available for most “Macrolepidoptera” (Schintlmeister 2008; Yakovlev et al. 2015; Zolotuhin 2015; Didmanidze 2016; Zolotuhin and Evdoshenko 2019; Zolotuhin and Nedoshivina 2021; Snegovaya and Petrov 2021) and for several “Microlepidoptera” (Anikin and Shchurov 2001). The fauna of most Lepidoptera families is studied very fragmentary, though in the recent years some significant faunal results have been obtained for southern Ossetia (Streltsov et al 2022a, b, 2024; Nedoshivina et al. 2023; Sinev et al. 2023) and the Republic of Dagestan (Ilyina et al. 2012; Poltavsky and Ilyina 2016; Dubatolov et al. 2021; Ustjuzhanin et al. 2022; Yakovlev et al. 2022; Tsvetkov 2023).

With this article we begin a series dedicated to the little-studied Lepidoptera families of Azerbaijan.

Geographically, Azerbaijan is located in the South Caucasus region of Eurasia. It lies between latitudes 38° and 42° N, and longitudes 44° and 51° E. The country has a landlocked exclave, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Three physical features dominate Azerbaijan: the Caspian Sea, whose shoreline forms a natural boundary to the east; the Greater Caucasus mountain range to the north; and the extensive flatlands at the country's center. There are also three mountain ranges, the Greater and Lesser Caucasus, and the Talysh Mountains, together covering approximately 40% of the country. The highest peak of Azerbaijan is Mount Bazardüzü 4,466 m, while the lowest point lies in the Caspian Sea –28 m. Over half of Azerbaijan's landmass consists of mountain ridges, crests, highlands, and plateaus which rise up to hypsometric levels of 400–1000 meters (including the Middle and Lower lowlands), in some places (Talış, Jeyranchol-Ajinohur and Langabiz-Alat foreranges) up to 100–120 meters, and others from 0–50 meters and up (Qobustan, Absheron). Nine out of eleven existing climate zones are present in Azerbaijan. The maximum annual precipitation falls in Lenkoran (1,600 to 1,800 mm) and the minimum in Absheron (200 to 350 mm). Azerbaijan's flora consists of more than 4,500 species of higher plants (Askerov 2008). Due to the unique climate in Azerbaijan, the flora is much richer in the number of species than the flora of the other republics of the South Caucasus. 66 percent of the species growing in the whole Caucasus can be found in Azerbaijan. The main areas of plant diversity in Azerbaijan are the highlands of Nakhchivan (60% of the species occur here), the Kura-Araz plain (40%), the Devechi-Kuba region east of the Greater Caucasus (38%), the centre of the Lesser Caucasus (29%), Gobustan (26.6%), the Lenkoran region in the Talish Mountains (27%), and the Absheron region (22%). There are over 400 species of plants endemic to Azerbaijan (including ten endemic species of lichens). The coun-

try lies within four ecoregions: Caspian Hyrcanian mixed forests, Caucasus mixed forests, Eastern Anatolian montane steppe, and Azerbaijan shrub desert and steppe (Dinerstein et al. 2017).

The first information about the Pyraloidea fauna (Lepidoptera) of Transcaucasia in general and the modern territory of Azerbaijan in particular appeared after the expeditions of H.T. Christoph (Hugo Theodor Christoph (1831–1894)) in Transcaucasia and Northern Iran in 1881, 1882 and 1883. The results of these expeditions were published by him and Grand Duke N.M. Romanoff (Christoph 1876, 1887, 1893; Romanoff 1887) and to this day are the most complete reports on Pyraloidea of Azerbaijan. In total, he lists 134 species. Some data is also contained in the well-known catalog of G.I. Radde (1899), the first volume of which is devoted to invertebrate animals, including Lepidoptera. Radde lists 66 species of Pyraloidea for different locations. For almost the entire 20th century, the Pyraloidea of Transcaucasia were not the subject of close attention of researchers. Information about Pyraloidea of Azerbaijan in modern works is scarce and they are mentioned either in reviews of agricultural pests (Akhundova-Tuaeva 1947; Zagulyaev 1965; Vezirov et al. 1981; Jafarov 1982; Sinev 1999), or incidentally in articles devoted to the fauna of Azerbaijan in general and adjacent regions (Bogachev 1951; Ivinskis 1986; Poltavsky et al. 2013). Most of this information was taken into account in the works of F. Slamka (Slamka 2006; 2008; 2013; 2019), where 46 species are listed in the text and on maps.

Materials and methods

This article is based on materials collected by Nataly Snegovaya, Nazar Shapoval and Roman Yakovlev in the nine localities of Azerbaijan (Fig. 1). A total of 92 species of Pyraloidea were identified, of which 48 were found for the first time (marked “*” in the table). In addition to our own materials, we summarized all available literature sources and included the data available in Table 1. The order of genera is adopted as in the Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia (Sinev et al. 2009; Sinev, Streltsov 2009). This review can serve as a basis for further research.

List of collecting localities

1. **Azerbaijan**, Salyan District, Shirvan Reserve, 39°39'38"N 49°20'25" E, -20 m, 13-14.05.2023, N. Shapoval & R. Yakovlev leg. (Fig. 2);
2. **Azerbaijan**, near Mingechaur, Kura Valley, 40°47'47" N 47°3'12" E, 100 m, 16-17.05.2023, N. Snegovaya, N. Shapoval & R. Yakovlev leg. (Fig. 3);
3. **Azerbaijan**, Agdash District, Bozdag Ridge, near Turianchai, 40°43'17" N 47°30'11" E, 140 m, 18-19.05.2023, N. Snegovaya, N. Shapoval & R. Yakovlev leg. (Fig. 4);

4. **Azerbaijan**, Talysh Mts., Masalli District, 25 km SW Masalli, 38°56'53" N 48°28'42" E, 380 m, 21.05.2023, N. Snegovaya, N. Shapoval & R. Yakovlev leg. (Fig. 5);
5. **Azerbaijan**, Baku city, Garadagh District, near Gobustan, 40°12'42" N 49°12'33" E, 310 m, 22.05.2023, N. Shapoval & R. Yakovlev leg. (Fig. 6);
6. **Azerbaijan**, Masalli District, Massaly, Miyanku village, 38°53'52"N, 48°39'59"E, 24-27.07.2023, N. Snegovaya leg.;
7. **Azerbaijan**, Ordubad District, Agdere village, 39°6'40"N, 45°54'55"E, 23-24.08.2023, N. Snegovaya leg.;
8. **Azerbaijan**, Yevlakh city, near the Kainat hotel, 40°36'52"N, 47°8'51"E, 4.07.2023, N. Snegovaya leg.;
9. **Azerbaijan**, Lerik, Gosmalyan village, 38°40'22"N, 48°22'15"E, 5.06.2023, N. Snegovaya leg.

The collections were carried out by manual collection during the daytime and at dusk, as well as on light screens Naturaliste-180 (using lamps OSRAM-160, 250 W) (Fig. 7) and autonomous light traps ENTOSPHINX lamp UV LED 12 V/19,2W (equipped with diodes 240 UV LED) (Fig. 8). The form of the map of Azerbaijan was taken from an open Internet resource (<https://www.bluegreenatlas.com>).

Figure 1. Map of Azerbaijan with collecting localities.

Figures 2–3. 2. Salyan District, Shirvan Reserve (photo by R. Yakovlev). 3. Near Mingechaur, Kura Valley (photo by R. Yakovlev).

Figures 4–5. 4. Agdash District, Bozdag Ridge, near Turianchai (photo by R. Yakovlev).
5. Talysh Mts., Masalli District, 25 km SW Masalli (photo by R. Yakovlev).

Figures 6–7. 6. Near Gobustan (photo by R. Yakovlev). 7. Light screens Naturaliste-180 (photo by R. Yakovlev).

Figure 8. Autonomous light traps (photo by R. Yakovlev).

Result

Table 1. List of Pyraloidea of Azerbaijan

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	<i>Aphomia foedella</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244; Radde, 1899: 439)								
2	<i>Aphomia gularis</i> (Zeller, 1877)	Azerbaijan: (Vezirov et al., 1981: 74)								
3	* <i>Aphomia sociella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
4	<i>Lamoria anella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244, Radde, 1899: 438), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2006: 54)								
5	* <i>Lamoria zelleri</i> (Joannis, 1932)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	<i>Achroia grisella</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	Azerbaijan: Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 384)								
7	<i>Galleria mellonella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 384)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
8	<i>Endotricha flammealis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243)								
9	<i>Hypotia colchicalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Radde, 1899: 436)								
10	* <i>Hypotia infulalis</i> Lederer, 1858	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	<i>Hypotia massilialis</i> (Duponchel, 1832)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 14; Radde, 1899: 436)								
12	<i>Hypotia proximalis</i> Christophh, 1882	Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Helenendorf (Christoph, 1882: 116; Christoph, 1887: 15; Radde, 1899: 436)								
13	<i>Synaphe antennalis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 14; Radde, 1899: 436)								
14	<i>Synaphe armenialis</i> (Lederer, 1870)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
15	<i>Synaphe bombycalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
16	<i>Synaphe moldavica</i> (Esper, 1794)	Azerbaijan: Kussary, Bilasuvar, Shemakha, Salyan (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
17	<i>Stemmatophora brunnealis</i> (Treitschke, 1829)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
18	<i>Hypsopygia (Hypsopygia) costalis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 242; Radde, 1899: 436)								
19	<i>Hypsopygia (Ocrasa) glaucinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 242; Radde, 1899: 436), Helenendorf, Zagatala, Hankynda (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
20	<i>Pyralis farinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Ordubad, Lenkoran (Radde, 1899: 436), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Zagulayev, 1965: 122; Slamka, 2006: 42)								
21	<i>Pyralis kacheticalis</i> (Christoph, 1893)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Eldar, Muganli (Christoph, 1893: 96; Slamka, 2006: 40)								
22	<i>Pyralis perversalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad, Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 14)								
23	<i>Aglossa pinguinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 436)								
24	<i>Aglossa caprealis</i> (Hübner, 1809)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 16; Radde, 1899: 436)								
25	<i>Pempeliella ornatella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2019: 34)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
26	* <i>Keradere tengstroemiella</i> (Erschoff, 1874)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
27	<i>Sciota rhenella</i> (Zincken, 1818)	Azerbaijan: Absheron (Akhundova-Tuaeva, 1947: 142)								
28	<i>Psorosa dahliella</i> (Treitschke, 1832)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Radde, 1899: 438)								
29	* <i>Psorosa nucleolella</i> (Möschler, 1866)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
30	* <i>Psorosa</i> sp. (<i>marshella</i> sp. group)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
31	* <i>Selagia argyrella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775])	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
32	<i>Selagia spadicella</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244)								
33	* <i>Pima boisduvaliella</i> (Guenée, 1845)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
34	* <i>Etiella zinckenella</i> (Treitschke, 1832)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	* <i>Merulempista cingillella</i> (Zeller, 1846)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
36	* <i>Merulempista rubicundella</i> (Rebel, 1911)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
37	* <i>Myrllaea pittionii</i> (Amsel, 1950)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
38	<i>Oncocera semirubella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244; Radde, 1899: 438), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Slamka, 2019: 118)								
39	* <i>Laodamia faecella</i> (Zeller, 1839)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
40	<i>Rhodophaea formosa</i> (Haworth, 1811)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244; Radde, 1899: 438)								
41	* <i>Pseudophycita deformella</i> (Möschler, 1866)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
42	* <i>Phycita diaphana</i> (Staudinger, 1870)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
43	* <i>Phycita kurdistanella</i> Amsel, 1954	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
44	* <i>Phycita meliella</i> (Mann, 1864)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
45	<i>Phycita poteriella</i> (Zeller, 1846)	Azerbaijan: (Sinev, 1999: 152; Slamka, 2019: 158)								
46	* <i>Ceutholopha isidis</i> (Zeller, 1867)	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
47	<i>Epischmia prodromella</i> (Hübner, 1799)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Goygol (Ivinskis, 1986: 111, 113)								
48	<i>Acrobasis repandana</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
49	<i>Acrobasis advenella</i> (Zincken, 1818)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
		Azerbaijan: widespread (Vezirov et al., 1981)								
50	<i>Acrobasis consociella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Azerbaijan: Ganja, Dashkesan (Jafarov, 1982: 34)								
51	<i>Apomyelois ceratoniae</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Everywhere (Vezirov, Effendi, Aliyeva, 1981: 69), Caucasus (Zagulayev, 1965: 191)								
52	* <i>Eurhodope cinerea</i> (Staudinger, 1879)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
53	<i>Eurhodope rosella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Goygol (Poltavsky, Sinev, Matov, 2013: 289)								
54	* <i>Christophia christophorella</i> (Ragonot, 1887)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
55	* <i>Prorophora curvibasella</i> Ragonot, 1887	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
56	* <i>Myelois cinctipalpella</i> Christoph, 1877	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
57	<i>Myelois circumvoluta</i> (Fourcroy, 1785)	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244; Radde, 1899: 438)								
58	* <i>Myelois fuscicostella</i> Mann, 1861	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
59	* <i>Pterothrixidia squalidella</i> (Eversmann, 1842)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
60	* <i>Arimania komaroffi</i> (Ragonot, 1888)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
61	* <i>Amasyana amanella</i> (Zerny in Osthelder, 1935)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
62	* <i>Rowanduzia diplocapna</i> (Meyrick, 1937)	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+
63	* <i>Asalebria venustella</i> (Ragonot, 1887)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
64	<i>Pristocerella solskyi</i> (Christoph, 1877)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
		Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2019: 112)								
65	<i>Neopristocerella deltagrammella</i> (Ragonot, 1888)	Azerbaijan: Helendorf [Goygol] (Slamka, 2019: 113)								
66	<i>Slamkania sordida</i> (Staudinger, 1879)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Slamka, 2019)								
67	* <i>Gymnancyla gilvella</i> Ragonot, 1887	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
68	* <i>Gymnancyla sieversi</i> (Christoph, 1877)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
69	* <i>Eccopisa effractella</i> Zeller, 1848	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
70	* <i>Euzophera fuliginosella</i> (Heinemann, 1865)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
71	<i>Nyctegretis lineana</i> (Scopoli, 1786)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Mugan (Christoph, 1886: 244)								
72	* <i>Ancylosis faustinella</i> (Zeller, 1867)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
73	* <i>Ancylosis delicatella</i> Möschler, 1860	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
74	* <i>Ancylosis cinnamomella</i> (Duponchel, 1836)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
75	* <i>Ancylosis substratellum</i> (Christoph, 1877)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
76	<i>Ancylosis rhodochrella</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244)								
77	<i>Homoeosoma nebulella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951: 35)								
78	* <i>Homoeosoma sinuella</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
79	* <i>Phycitodes maritima</i> (Tengström, 1848)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+
80	* <i>Phycitodes saxicola</i> (Vaughan, 1870)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
81	<i>Plodia interpunctella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951: 385)								

No	Species	Localities																		
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9										
82	<i>Ephestia elutella</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Zagulayev, 1965: 153)																		
83	<i>Ephestia kuehniella</i> Zeller, 1879	Azerbaijan: everywhere (Zagulayev, 1965: 142), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385)																		
84	<i>Cadra cautella</i> (Walker, 1863)	Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951, Zagulayev, 1965), everywhere (Vezirov et al., 1981)																		
85	<i>Cadra calidella</i> (Guenée, 1845)	Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Vezirov et al., 1981: 68), Transcaucasia (Zagulayev, 1965: 172)																		
86	* <i>Cadra furcatella</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
87	<i>Cadra figulilella</i> (Gregson, 1871)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Zagulayev, 1965: 178; Vezirov et al., 1981)																		
88	* <i>Anerastia lotella</i> (Hübner, 1813)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
89	<i>Coenochroa ablutella</i> (Zeller, 1839)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244)																		
90	<i>Ematheudes punctella</i> (Treitschke, 1833)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Eldar, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 37), Eldar (Radde, 1899: 437), Ordubad, Goygol, Eldar steppe, Gumbashi (Poltavsky et al., 2013: 287–288)																		
91	* <i>Saluria maculivittella</i> Ragonot, 1887	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
92	<i>Chilo luteellus</i> (Motschulsky, 1866)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 43)																		
93	<i>Chilo phragmitellus</i> (Hubner, [1805])	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243; Christoph, 1887: 43; Radde, 1899: 438)																		
94	* <i>Glaucobaris euchromiella</i> (Ragonot, 1895)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
95	<i>Euchromius bella</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244)																		
96	<i>Euchromius jaxartella</i> (Erschoff, 1874)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 47)																		
97	<i>Euchromius ocella</i> (Haworth, 1811)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Djulfa, Istisu, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 47), Eldar, Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 438)																		
98	* <i>Euchromius mouchai</i> Bleszyński, 1961	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
99	<i>Euchromius ramburiellus</i> (Duponchel, 1836)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran, Helenendorf, Eldar (Christoph, 1887: 47)																		

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
100	<i>Euchromius pulverosa</i> (Christoph, 1886)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 47)								
101	<i>Calamotropha paludella</i> (Hübner, 1824)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243; Christoph, 1887: 44)								
102	<i>Chrysoteuchia culmella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243)								
103	<i>Crambus pratella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 44)								
104	<i>Crambus perlella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Hankynda (Christoph, 1887: 47)								
105	<i>Crambus pascuellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Radde, 1899: 438)								
106	<i>Agriphila inquinatella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Zagatala (Christoph, 1887: 46)								
107	<i>Agriphila geniculea</i> (Haworth, 1811)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 46)								
108	<i>Catoptria incertella</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)	Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2008: 72)								
109	* <i>Catoptria mytilella</i> (Hübner, 1805)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
110	<i>Catoptria falsella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Zagatala (Christoph, 1887: 45)								
111	* <i>Catoptria pinella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
112	<i>Metacrambus carectellus</i> (Zeller, 1847)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Eldar (Radde, 1899: 438)								
113	<i>Xanthocrambus saxonellus</i> (Zincken, 1821)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 45)								
114	<i>Chrysocrambus craterellus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243; Radde, 1899: 438), Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 44)								
115	<i>Chrysocrambus linetellus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Hankynda, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 44), Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 438)								
116	<i>Thisanotia chrysonuchella</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 45)								
117	<i>Pediasia jucundellus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1847)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 45)								
118	<i>Pediasia contaminella</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 244; Radde, 1899: 438)								
119	<i>Platytes cerussella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 44)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
120	<i>Ancylolomia palpella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 44)								
121	<i>Talis quercella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: (Bogachev, 1951)								
122	<i>Scirpophaga praelata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243; Radde, 1899: 438), Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 43)								
123	<i>Schoenobius gigantella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243; Radde, 1899: 438), Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 43)								
124	<i>Donacaula nilotica</i> (Zeller, 1867)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 43)								
125	<i>Scoparia absconditalis</i> (Christoph, 1887)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 17)								
126	<i>Scoparia ambigualis</i> (Treitschke, 1829)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 18)								
127	* <i>Scoparia basistrigalis</i> Knaggs, 1866	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
128	<i>Scoparia ingrattella</i> (Zeller, 1846)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 19)								
129	<i>Scoparia pyralella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Kussary (Christoph, 1887: 19)								
130	<i>Scoparia staudingeralis</i> Mabilie, 1869	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 19; Radde, 1889: 436)								
131	<i>Eudonia valesialis</i> (Duponchel, 1832)	Azerbaijan: Zakataly (Christoph, 1887: 19)								
132	<i>Eudonia lacustrata</i> (Panzer, 1804)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 19)								
133	<i>Eudonia mercurella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Muganly (Christoph, 1887: 19)								
134	<i>Anarpia incertalis</i> (Duponchel, 1832)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 17; Radde, 1899: 436)								
135	<i>Gesneria centuriella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 17)								
136	<i>Elophila nymphaeata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 43), Lenkoran (Radde, 1899: 438)								
137	<i>Cataclysta lemnata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Lerik (Radde, 1899: 438)								
138	<i>Parapoynx stratiotata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243; Christoph, 1887: 43)								
139	<i>Hyperlais dulcinalis</i> (Treitschke, 1835)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 27; Radde, 1899: 437)								
140	<i>Stiphrometasia monialis</i> (Erschoff, 1872)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 26; Radde, 1899: 436)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
141	<i>Cybalomia pentadalis</i> (Lederer, 1855)	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 40; Radde, 1899: 437)								
142	<i>Cybalomia gratiosalis</i> Christoph in Christoph, 1887	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 40)								
143	<i>Metaxmeste phrygialis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243)								
144	<i>Cynaeda dentalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25; Radde, 1899: 436)								
145	<i>Cynaeda superba</i> (Freyer, 1845)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Radde, 1899: 436)								
146	<i>Tegostoma baphialis</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Baku (Christoph, 1887: 25), Eldar (Radde, 1899: 436)								
147	<i>Tegostoma concinnalis</i> (Chrystoph, 1882)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25; Radde, 1899: 436)								
148	<i>Tegostoma lepidalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25; Radde, 1899: 436)								
149	<i>Tegostoma comparalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25; Radde, 1899: 436), Ordubad, Eldar steppe, Goygol, Gumbashi (Poltavsky et al., 2013: 284)								
150	<i>Tegostoma moeschleri</i> (Christoph, 1862)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25), Ordubad, Eldar steppe, Goygol (Poltavsky et al., 2013)								
151	<i>Aeschremon disparalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad, Baku (Christoph, 1887: 26), Ordubad (Radde, 1899: 436), Ordubad, Eldar steppe, Goygol (Poltavsky et al., 2013: 284)								
152	<i>Epascestria pustulalis</i> (Hübner, [1823])	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 24; Radde, 1899: 436), Barda, Goygol (Poltavsky et al., 2013)								
153	<i>Aporodes dentifascialis</i> Christoph, 1887	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 20)								
154	<i>Aporodes floralis</i> (Hübner, 1809)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 19), Absheron (Akhundova-Tuaeva, 1947)								
155	<i>Turania pentodontalis</i> Erschoff, 1874	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 25)								
156	<i>Ephelis cruentalis</i> (Geyer, 1832)	Azerbaijan: Ajikent (Christoph, 1887: 24)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
157	<i>Evergestis aenealis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 38)								
158	<i>Evergestis desertalis</i> (Hübner, 1813)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 39; Radde, 1899: 437)								
159	<i>Evergestis forficalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Bilasuvar, Geok-Tapa (Christoph, 1887: 38)								
160	<i>Evergestis frumentalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Mugan (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Nucha, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 39), Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437)								
161	<i>Evergestis limbata</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 39)								
162	<i>Evergestis manglisalis</i> Erschoff, 1877	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 39)								
163	<i>Evergestis nomadalis</i> (Lederer, 1872)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 39), Karabagh (Radde, 1899: 437)								
164	<i>Evergestis politalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 39)								
165	<i>Evergestis segetalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	Azerbaijan: Hankynda (Christoph, 1887: 39)								
166	<i>Evergestis sophialis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Azerbaijan: Istisu, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 39)								
167	<i>Evergestis subfuscalis</i> (Staudinger, 1881)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 38; Radde, 1899: 437)								
168	<i>Loxostege sticticalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385; Slamka, 2013: 23)								
169	<i>Loxostege clathralis</i> (Hübner, 1813)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad, Ajikent (Christoph, 1887: 37), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 4)								
170	<i>Loxostege deliblatica</i> Szent-Ivány & Uhrík-Meszáros, 1942	Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2013: 12)								
171	<i>Loxostege mucosalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)	Azerbaijan: Eldar (Radde, 1899: 437)								
172	<i>Ecpyrrhorrhoe diffusalis</i> (Guenée, 1854)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 34; Radde, 1899: 437)								
173	<i>Ecpyrrhorrhoe rubiginalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Nucha (Christoph, 1887: 34), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 25)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
174	<i>Achyra nudalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-
		Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Ordubad, Eldar, Istusu, Agstafa, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 37), Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 26)								
175	<i>Palepicorsia ustrinalis</i> (Christoph, 1877)	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Eldar, Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 36), Eldar (Radde, 1899: 437), Eldar, Goygol, Jafarkhan (Poltavsky et al., 2013: 286), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 27)								
176	<i>Paracorsia repandalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 32; Radde, 1899: 437)								
177	<i>Paratalanta cultralis</i> (Staudinger, 1867)	Azerbaijan: Geok-Tapa (Christoph, 1887: 30)								
178	<i>Paratalanta hyalinalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Eldar, Kedabeg, Ajikent (Christoph, 1887: 30), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
179	<i>Paratalanta pandalis</i> (Hübner, 1825)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243)								
180	<i>Pyrausta aerealis</i> (Hübner, 1793)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 28), Istisu, Odubad (Radde, 1899: 436–437)								
181	<i>Pyrausta aurata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437), Helenendorf, Hankynda, Ordubad, Zakatala, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 27), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 44)								
182	<i>Pyrausta castalis</i> Treitschke, 1829	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 26; Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
183	<i>Pyrausta cingulata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Eldar (Christoph, 1887: 26; Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
184	<i>Pyrausta despicata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2013)								
185	<i>Pyrausta falcatalis</i> Guenée, 1854	Azerbaijan: Kedabeg (Christoph, 1887: 27)								
186	<i>Pyrausta purpuralis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Nucha, Kedabeg, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 27), Ordubad, Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 46)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
187	<i>Pyrausta sanguinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 27), Helenendorf, Eldar (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 37)								
188	<i>Pyrausta limbopunctalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1849)	Azerbaijan: Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 27)								
189	* <i>Pyrasia gutturalis</i> (Staudinger, 1879)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
190	<i>Uresiphita gilvata</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 28; Radde, 1899: 437), Absheron (Akhundova-Tuaeva, 1947: 142), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 64)								
191	<i>Nascia ciliaris</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243)								
192	<i>Sitochroa palealis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Ordubad, Hankynda, Geok-Tapa (Christoph, 1887: 37), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 67)								
193	<i>Sitochroa verticalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Varvara, Ordubad, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 38), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 68)								
194	<i>Euclasta splendidalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Lenkoran, Elisavetpol (Christoph, 1887: 42), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 71)								
195	<i>Psammotis pulveralis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 38)								
196	<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Talysh (Christoph, 1887: 33), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385)								
197	<i>Anania coronata</i> (Hufnagel, 1767)	Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Eldar (Christoph, 1887: 34), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 85)								
198	<i>Anania ochrofascialis</i> (Christoph, 1882)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 41; Radde, 1899: 437), Ordubad, Eldar steppe, Goygol, Gobustan (Poltavsky et al., 2013), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 90)								
199	<i>Anania verbascalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Nucha (Christoph, 1887: 34), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 83)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
200	<i>Anania hortulata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Zakataly (Christoph, 1887: 26), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 96)								
201	<i>Anania fuscalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 34), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 97)								
202	<i>Anania terrealis</i> (Treitschke, 1829)	Azerbaijan: Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437)								
203	<i>Patania ruralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243; Radde, 1899: 437), Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 37), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 92)								
204	<i>Mecyna flavalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Ordubad, Lenkoran (Christoph, 1887: 28), Helenendorf, Ordubad (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 142)								
205	<i>Mecyna trinalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2013: 145)								
206	<i>Mecyna amasialis</i> (Staudinger, 1880)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 28; Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 149)								
207	<i>Mecyna marcidalis</i> (Fuchs, 1879)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph in Christoph, 1887: 28), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 148)								
208	<i>Mecyna subsequalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Istisu (Christoph, 1887: 32), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 153)								
209	<i>Diasemia reticularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Azerbaijan: (Slamka, 2013: 158)								
210	<i>Udea bipunctalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)	Azerbaijan: Ajikent, Kedabeg (Christoph, 1887: 36)								
211	<i>Udea ferrugalis</i> (Hübner, 1796)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243 Christoph, 1887: 36)								
212	<i>Udea languidalis</i> (Eversmann, 1842)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
		Azerbaijan: Helenendorf, Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 35), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 107)								
213	<i>Udea olivalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Azerbaijan: Kedabeg (Christoph, 1887: 36)								
214	<i>Udea praepetalis</i> (Lederer, 1869)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 33), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 138)								
215	<i>Udea vastalis</i> (Christoph in Christoph, 1887)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph in Christoph, 1887: 33), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 114)								

No	Species	Localities								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
216	<i>Nomophila noctuella</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+
		Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Lenkoran, Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437), Absheron (Akhundova-Tuaeva, 1947: 142), Azerbaijan (Bogachev, 1951: 385)								
217	<i>Agrotera nemoralis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Azerbaijan: Lenkoran (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf (Christoph, 1887: 42), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
218	* <i>Duponchelia fovealis</i> Zeller, 1847	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
219	<i>Dolicharthria bruguieralis</i> (Duponchel, 1833)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad, Djebail (Christoph, 1887: 42), Ordubad (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013: 168)								
220	<i>Dolicharthria punctalis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Azerbaijan: Mugan (Christoph, 1886: 243), Helenendorf, Ordubad, Hankynda (Christoph, 1887: 42), Eldar, Helenendorf (Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
221	<i>Dolicharthria intervacatalis</i> (Christoph, 1877)	Azerbaijan: Ordubad (Christoph, 1887: 42; Radde, 1899: 437), Azerbaijan (Slamka, 2013)								
222	<i>Dolicharthria stigmosalis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1848)	Azerbaijan: Talysh (Christoph, 1886: 243)								

Faunistic and systematic notes

**Hypotia infulalis* Lederer, 1858

The species is widespread in the Mediterranean region and is known from Turkey (Leraut 2014). The northernmost find.

**Psorosa* sp. (*marshella* sp. group)

An unidentified species from the *marshella* group, possibly new to science, additional materials and research are required.

**Ceutholopha isidis* (Zeller, 1867)

The species is distributed in Africa, the Middle East, and is locally occurring in Great Britain and Corsica (Leraut 2014). Relatively recently, the species was discovered in Turkey (Akin 2018). The most northeastern records.

Discussion

Thanks to this, a complete summary of the Pyraloidea fauna of Azerbaijan was obtained, including 222 species. This summary can serve as a basis for further research.

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